

Cyclic voltammetric studies of some copper(II)-carboxylate complexes in aqueous medium

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Electrochemical behaviours of copper(II)-trichloroacetate, -monochloroacetate, -acetate and copper(II)-propionate have been studied in aqueous medium by means of cyclic voltammetry at glassy carbon electrode. The CV parameters are calculated. It has been observed that all these complexes involve two step redox processes. The first step involves a quasi-reversible diffusion-controlled, single electron charge transfer ($\text{Cu}^{2+}/+$), while the second step involves a totally irreversible single-electron transfer ($\text{Cu}^{+}/0$).

Prasad *et al.*¹ studied the X-ray K-absorption spectra of some copper(II)-carboxylate complexes involving metal-metal interaction. Copper(II/I) electron transfer reactions are currently of interest because the structural differences between the two oxidation states place unusual constraints on the electron transfer kinetics². In this paper we describe the cyclic voltammetric, coulometric and electronic absorption

spectral studies of copper(II)-trichloroacetate, -monochloroacetate, -acetate and copper(II)-propionate complexes in aqueous medium.

Results and discussion

The cyclic voltammetric parameters for 1 mM copper(II)-carboxylate complexes in aqueous 0.2 M sodium perchlorate are given in the Table 1. The initial cathodic scan indi-

Table 1. Cyclic voltammetric parameters for 1 mM Cu(II)-carboxylate complexes in aqueous 0.2 M NaClO₄

Complex	Scan rate/ mV s ⁻¹	E_{pc1}/mV	E_{pa1}/mV	$I_{pc1}/\mu\text{A}$	$I_{pa1}/\mu\text{A}$	$\Delta E_p/\text{mV}$	E^0/mV	I_{pa1}/I_{pc1}	E_{pc2}/mV
Cu(Cl ₃ CCOO) ₂ ·3H ₂ O	25	-10	+60	22.0	13.0	70	+25	0.57	-475
	50	-20	+70	31.0	18.0	90	+25	0.58	-520
	100	-30	+70	44.0	25.0	100	+20	0.56	-550
	150	-40	+80	53.5	30.0	120	+20	0.56	-590
	200	-50	+80	62.0	35.0	130	+15	0.56	-630
Cu(ClCH ₂ COO) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	25	-30	+50	16.0	15.0	80	+10	0.94	-450
	50	-40	+50	22.5	19.0	90	+5	0.84	-490
	100	-50	+60	32.0	27.0	110	+5	0.84	-530
	150	-60	+60	38.0	32.5	120	0	0.85	-580
	200	-70	+70	45.0	38.0	140	0	0.84	-610
Cu(CH ₃ COO) ₂ ·H ₂ O	25	-40	+40	19.0	8.0	80	0	0.42	-470
	50	-50	+40	27.0	12.0	90	-5	0.44	-510
	100	-60	+50	37.0	15.5	110	-5	0.42	-560
	150	-70	+50	46.0	20.0	120	-10	0.43	-610
	200	-80	+60	54.0	23.0	140	-10	0.43	-650
Cu(CH ₃ CH ₂ COO) ₂ ·H ₂ O	25	-60	+10	17.0	7.5	70	-25	0.44	-475
	50	-65	+10	24.5	11.0	75	-25	0.44	-500
	100	-70	+20	33.5	15.0	90	-25	0.44	-540
	150	-75	+30	40.5	19.0	105	-20	0.46	-570
	200	-90	+30	47.0	22.0	120	-25	0.46	-620

$$E^0 = \frac{1}{2}(E_{pc1} + E_{pa1}); I_{pc2} \text{ is not measurable.}$$

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of copper(II)-acetate in aqueous 0.2 M NaClO₄ at scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹.

cated a reduction peak, $c_1(\text{Cu}^{2+/+})$ at -60 mV vs Ag/AgCl, while the reverse scan produced an oxidation peak, a_1 at $+50$ mV at scan rate 100 mV s^{-1} in the potential range from $+1.0$ to -0.25 V vs Ag/AgCl as shown in Fig. 1 (Table 1). A totally irreversible second cathodic peak, $c_2(\text{Cu}^{+/0})$ is produced at -0.560 V on extending the negative potential limit to -0.875 V (Fig. 1).

A perusal of Table 1 shows that the cathodic peak potential, E_{pc_1} becomes more negative and the anodic-to-cathodic peak potential separation, $\Delta E_p (= E_{pa_1} - E_{pc_1})$ varies from 70 to 140 mV with increasing scan rate. Both these observations are indicative of the quasi-reversible one-electron transfer process³⁻⁵. Constant potential coulometry at -0.2 V vs Ag/AgCl has confirmed the involvement of one electron per molecule of each of these complexes. The parameter ΔE_p can be assumed as a rough index of the degree of departure from electrochemical reversibility considering that for one electron charge transfer, ΔE_p is 60 mV. The plots of I_{pc_1} or I_{pa_1} vs the square root of scan rate ($v^{1/2}$) produce a straight line passing through origin, indicating that the electrode process is diffusion controlled³. The ratio of anodic peak current to the cathodic peak current (I_{pa_1}/I_{pc_1}) is less than unity. This clearly indicates that the copper(I)-carboxylate complex species are electrochemically unstable and that the electron transfer is followed by a chemical reaction^{3,4} (EC mechanism). The following reaction pathway may be proposed to explain the observed electrochemical data :

It should be mentioned that examples of small molecules co-ordination number invariant copper(II/I) couples are rare. Even more rare are those that are conformationally invariant⁶. The reduction of copper(II)-acetate by copper in pyridine or acetonitrile has been reported⁷ and that the copper(I)-acetate has a planar chain structure. It is apparent from Table 1 that the cathodic peak potentials (E_{pc_1}) for these copper(II)-carboxylate complexes differ slightly. This may be due to the fact that these complexes involve identical co-ordination environment in aqueous medium; copper(II) site involves approximately octahedral coordination with four oxygens from the two carboxylate groups in the xy plane and two less strongly bound oxygens of the water molecules at axial positions^{8,9}. The electronic absorption spectra of copper(II)-trichloroacetate, -monochloroacetate, -acetate and copper(II)-propionate complexes in aqueous solutions show a single $d-d$ band (ν_{max}) at about 12350, 12690, 12950 and 13120 cm^{-1} , respectively. These are assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ transition, suggesting a distorted octahedral co-ordination in these complexes. It is interesting to note that the cathodic peak potential (E_{pc_1}) for the $\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ couple (Table 1) becomes more negative (i.e., difficult reduction) with increasing frequency of the absorption maximum (ν_{max}) for these complexes.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR or similar grade. The copper(II)-carboxylate complexes chosen for the present study include; $\text{Cu}(\text{Cl}_3\text{C.COO})_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{ClCH}_2\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{.CH}_2\text{.COO})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. These complexes were prepared by following the procedure reported earlier^{8,10}. The purity of these complexes was confirmed in each case by chemical analyses.

Cyclic voltammetry experiments were carried out with a BAS model CVIB (U.S.A.) instrument having an electrochemical cell with a three electrode system. The working electrode was a glassy carbon electrode (GCE), platinum wire was used as an auxiliary electrode, and Ag/AgCl electrode was used as a reference electrode ($E^0 = +0.199$ V vs NHE). The cyclic voltammograms were recorded on an X -

Y recorder. All the cyclic voltammetry experiments were done in an inert atmosphere achieved by purging the cell solution with extra pure nitrogen for 15 min. All the experiments were performed at 25°. Constant potential coulometric measurements were carried out with BAS model CV-27 coupled with Omnigraphic recorder. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-VIS spectrophotometer UV-160 using matched 1 cm-path length quartz cell.

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